

IN-HABIT

GLOSSARY

IN-HABIT KEY-WORDS

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INTRODUCTION

This glossary defines a shared vocabulary among the partners of the H2020 IN-HABIT project. It will facilitate both the internal communication and cooperation among the partners during the implementation and the external communication of its objectives and actions towards a wider audience. The glossary is conceived as a component of the toolkit for the engagement of stakeholders, an essential instrument to outreach diverse social, professional and cultural groups through different language environments. As such, it will also be part of the Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach plan (DECO). The terms included here have been selected mainly on the basis of the terminology employed by the submitted project description, completed with relevant words that have emerged in the first phases of collaboration among the partners responsible for WP5, WP6, WP7 and WP8 and consultation with the four cities (WP1-4).

The main objectives of this activity are:

- to agree on a widely shared meaning of the terminology employed among the partners and to avoid misunderstandings and inconsistencies during the project;
- to disambiguate about possible different uses of the same words in specific contexts;
- to define in which context key terms should be used and to translate more expert/disciplinary terminology into common language accessible to the general public;
- to clarify the “jargon” employed in the project, and to select preferred versions among quasi-synonyms and confusing variants;
- to check correct translations in the four local languages of the PPPs and local specific uses and ambiguities.

The sharing of a common vocabulary belonging to IN-HABIT is an important step to create collaboration, to foster co-creation and, ultimately, to achieve common goals.

The definitions proposed here are not conceived as exhaustive and universal acceptations of multifaceted and often fuzzy words that are widely employed in multiple contexts and disciplinary environments; rather, they aim to circumscribe clear, shared, operational meanings of these terms within the specific objectives and practices promoted by this project. The additional purpose is to facilitate correct translations of the main language of the project into the four local languages, and to support simple and inclusive formulations of its key concepts for general non-expert audiences. Moreover, the glossary is completed by a list of bibliographic references validating the recognition process. This glossary is meant as a co-created common pool resource of IN-HABIT.

The terms examined include:

- specific terminologies introduced by IN-HABIT methods and approaches;
- keywords widely used in EU policy and planning needing a clear explanation and communication to project participants;
- thematic keywords that have a specific relevance in disciplinary fields but may not be univocally recognised across different fields and to a general public;
- technical terms and acronyms.

This document has been developed through a collaborative process involving the partners of WP5. Four workshops dedicated to the drafting of the glossary have been organised and facilitated by TSR. All the partners have participated and contributed with their own interpretations, adding multiple perspectives from the various disciplines involved in the IN-HABIT project. The results of the four workshops held online have been transcribed using a shared online Trello platform. Edited by TSR, the final text is therefore a result of a joint effort.

B

BASELINE ASSESSMENT

A baseline study is an analysis of the current and contextual situation to be outlined at the outset of a programme or a project. It provides an overview of information to be considered and analysed to establish the benchmark against which future progress can be assessed, monitored or comparisons made.

BENEFICIARY

Beneficiaries are citizens and social groups targeted by the actions deployed by the project. They are recipients of the positive effects resulting from the process independently from their level of engagement, whereas the **stakeholders** are supposed to claim a defined interest in the envisioned action and consciously engage in related initiatives. Ideally, the project wants to smooth the distinction between beneficiary and stakeholders through an inclusive engagement process.

BEHAVIOURAL GAMES

Behavioural games refer to the analysis of behaviours in strategic interactions among individuals. The assumption is that individuals' choices and decision-making are not only motivated by rational pursuit of self-interest but also by emotions, beliefs, social norms, rules of thumb, issues of self-control and other psychological aspects, which all place limits on individuals' rationality.

IN-HABIT will make use of behavioural games at different stages of the project, from the elicitation of individual preferences, for instance in fostering cooperation, to finding targeted solutions to collective problems and also to evaluating the impact of new measures.

C

CITIZEN SCIENCE

Citizen Science refers to the engagement of the general public in scientific research activities. Citizen Science implies that the knowledge, resources, competence and skills of citizens have to be included in order to make cities' solutions effective and useful for the citizens they are meant for.

CITIZEN SCIENCE INCLUSION MECHANISM (CSIM)

The CSIM in IN-HABIT is designed to embed the engagement scheme in the impact assessment process (see **Systemic Impact Framework**). It consists of a four-level assessment method envisaged to include local citizens and representatives from each city's **IN-HUB** within the process.

First level: the local/**community activators** selected and trained in WP5 will be engaged as co-researchers to run interviews and focus groups with local citizens in the local language.

Second level: around 15 local **community representatives/observers**, namely people who are expected to live in the project areas for the whole duration of the intervention, will be used as neighbourhood observers and periodically consulted through qualitative interviews and focus groups. Among them, a subgroup of “special users” with specific diversity profiles will be involved by means of **behavioural games**, observations and interviews.

Third level: a wider group of comprehensive **stakeholders**, including local institutions, enterprises, NGOs and neighbourhood committees, will be used as open data providers, as well as involved in local focus groups.

Fourth level: the general public of citizens, including tourists and people occasionally attending the city areas, will be periodically interviewed using Mobile Experience Sampling (see **IN-HABIT App**).

CO-CREATED COMMON POOL RESOURCES (CCPR)

Common Pool Resources (CPR) are resources owned, managed and used by the community. They might be easy to access but difficult to preserve. They are subject to being overused or wasted, thus reducing their availability for others. They are often a result of social relations based on interdependence and cooperation.

IN-HABIT will mobilise CPR by activating **People-Public-Private Partnerships** (PPPPs) to improve **inclusive health and wellbeing**.

CO-CREATION

Co-creation is a comprehensive term that encompasses a large set of collaborative approaches throughout different disciplinary fields. At its simplest, co-creation refers to the active involvement of end-users in various stages of the production process. It gained traction in the 1990s, initially in the business world, in reference to the involvement of customers in the ‘co-creation’ of the products they would consume. It migrated into the world of social and economic development and academic research with the new focus on commons, as in the work of Elinor Ostrom. During recent years, it has gained emphasis in a number of disciplines, including creative and artistic practices as transformative tools and agents of social innovation. Co-creation puts a major significance on pooling resources, sharing knowledge and creating the conditions for collaboratively managing change, while the term **co-design** focuses more on the co-production of specific solutions.

CO-DESIGN

Co-design is a practice in which people collaborate or connect their knowledge, skills and resources in order to carry out a design task. It produces new knowledge as people develop and experiment with (new) ideas around a matter of concern and as they engage in negotiations around the development of these ideas.

E

EMPOWERMENT

Empowerment has been defined by the World Bank as the process to improve the capacity of an individual or group to make decisions in order to transform choices into actions and desired results. There are several elements that characterise empowerment as a category: (1) The importance of individuals and communities when making decisions on issues that directly affect them, being the ultimate protagonists of the same. (2) The importance of processes and methodologies to make empowerment effective and as an inherent part of it. Methodologically, empowerment is related to action-research methods. (3) Empowerment as an element that allows acquiring a new social, economic and political dimension for groups in disadvantaged conditions. And (4) empowerment as an expression of democratic societies, with participatory decision-making built under criteria of civic responsibility.

On this basis, empowerment can be understood to manifest itself in three areas of influence and improvement for a person:

- Personal efficiency: those involved develop the ability to do things for themselves through the acquisition of skills such as communication and specific problem-solving skills.
- Critical autonomy: ability to think for oneself as an integral part of the empowerment process.
- Community involvement: ability to work with a group to achieve social change.

F

FRAMEWORK FOR CHANGE

It is the conceptual map proposed by the partner TSR (leading WP5 on the engagement process) to frame and steer any inclusive transformative process. Its scope is to facilitate the alignment of the essential variables of the transition path, namely language, procedures, expectations and time. The framework considers the four main dimensions of change: the spatial (development, regeneration, mobility), the social (H&W, equality, cohesion, **mindset change**), the strategic (planning, policy) and the creative (economic development, capacity building), aiming at their integration into a fully-fledged holistic approach. It defines a set of eight key moments of the transformative process, to which the IN-HABIT **GDEI Stakeholder Engagement Toolkit** provides a tailored set of tools for the inclusive management of the IN-HUBs.

G

GENDER, DIVERSITY, EQUITY AND INCLUSION (GDEI) APPROACH

A Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) perspective aims at promoting diversity, equity, and inclusion by considering individual characteristics and circumstances. As a whole, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion efforts seek to create meaningful, systemic change toward more equitable environments by:

- Including considerations of the way people differ and encompassing their different characteristics, such as, but not limited to, ethnicity, gender, disability, sexual orientation, religion and belief;
- Promoting fair treatment, access, opportunity, and advancement for all people, while at the same time striving to identify and eliminate barriers that have prevented the full participation of some groups (equity);
- Creating environments in which any individual or group can be and feel welcomed, respected, supported and valued (participation).

IN-HABIT adds gender to the DEI perspective, as it aims to particularly integrate a gender approach into its activities, with a view to promoting equality and equity in health and well-being between women and men. Besides biological factors, social norms and stereotypes also affect the health and well-being status of women and men differently. Among its primary goals, IN-HABIT aims to investigate challenges and develop innovative solutions in order to boost equity and inclusion in health and well-being at an urban level, with a particular focus on gender and diversity. In addition, in all its activities, IN-HABIT stands for and implements fair treatment of any underrepresented group, as well as fair and non-binary language.

GENDER, DIVERSITY, EQUITY AND INCLUSION (GDEI) INDICATORS

Gender, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion Indicators refer to quantitative measures of the extent of inequality experienced by disadvantaged social groups, often - but not exclusively - those covered by equality legislation.

GDEI indicators are helpful for establishing **baselines**, monitoring progress towards established equality objectives and also robustly assessing the impact of interventions.

IN-HABIT will make use of context-based GDEI indicators, including in a range of socio-economic factors and with emphasis on health and wellbeing, in order to assess the impact of the project's interventions.

GDEI STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT TOOLKIT

The Gender, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (GDEI) Stakeholders Engagement Toolkit is a comprehensive compendium of resources to support the establishment of the local **IN-HUBs** and the development of the **Inclusive Transition Pathways**. The aim of the IN-HABIT toolkit is to provide a set of guidelines, methods and tools for the wider engagement of **stakeholders** in

the **PPPPs** with specific attention to GDEI. It will include instructions for stakeholder mapping and local needs assessment, selection criteria, incentive mechanisms, structure, working rules and diversity management procedures, co-design methodology, and all the necessary guidelines and templates for the creation and management of the four local **IN-HUBs**. The toolkit will be the basis for the training process of the local community activators and will provide a reference set for the **ITW** established in the cities of Cordoba, Lucca, Nitra and Riga. It will support the accomplishment of a fully inclusive process of **co-creation**, co-design, co-management and co-monitoring of the innovative solutions envisioned by the four local **PPPPs**, with specific attention to the engagement of **stakeholders** who are less represented and more at risk of exclusion.

The toolkit is a living set of guidelines, methods and tools, and it will be adapted throughout the entire process based on the needs coming from the contextual application of tools to the specific issues of the territories and the feedback of the local communities using it. Its purpose is to provide a set of flexible instruments to support the development of solutions tailored to the peculiarities of the local communities and to support their transferability to other territories. The toolkit is created through a collaborative process steered by WP5 Lead Partner TSR in which the partners share methods and approaches to define a specific IN-HABIT methodology.

GENDER LANDSCAPE

Gender landscape refers to the gendered dimension of urban living. It recognises that people use the urban space differently because of various gendered structures, from the division of work, both paid and unpaid, to the role as carers, community leaders and networkers. It also considers how gender and sexuality are portrayed in communities, towns, cities and regions from a gender equality and diversity perspective. Viewing families, communities, towns, cities and regions from a gender equality and diversity perspective requires understanding of the main differences affecting the use of urban space.

GREEN AND SUSTAINABLE MOBILITY CORRIDOR

Green corridors in cities are linear natural infrastructures that connect green and open spaces to form a larger green urban network. These networks provide habitats and resources for urban wildlife and public services to urban populations. In urban settings, Green and Sustainable Mobility Corridors improve ecologically mobility networks and open public spaces. They further promote the creation of mixed land use (residential, commercial, education, recreation etc.).

The Cordoba green and sustainable corridor is targeted to reduce CO2 emissions through the **co-design**, co-deployment and co-management of sustainable mobility infrastructures (e.g., bike paths, service stations, parking lots, recharging spots, etc.) and **Nature Based Solutions** (e.g., therapy gardens, sustainable street furniture and playgrounds, recreational/relaxing areas, interactive, renewable and smart creative lighting, etc.), to increase residents' well being and health. The redesign of this space aims to clash the existing exclusion patterns, attracting the attention of local people and tourists visiting the cultural site towards the neglected neighbourhood, and to act as a trigger to increase residents' health and wellbeing through culture and heritage, and new job opportunities (e.g., bike or electric bike renting, **NBS** maintenance, urban gardening and organic vegetable production, bars and cafés).

H

HUMAN-ANIMAL BOND

The human-animal bond is a mutually beneficial and dynamic relationship between people and animals that is influenced by behaviours essential to the health and wellbeing of both. This includes, among other things, emotional, psychological and physical interactions of people, animals and the environment.

HUMAN-ANIMAL POLICY

Human-Animal Policy refers to those policies and actions that include the **human-animal bond** as part of the decision-making process at the community level.

IN-HABIT will promote new **nature based solutions** based on human-animal interactions in order to improve the health and wealth in the communities involved. IN-HABIT will look at how visionary and integrated actions around human and animal links might support the mobility and inclusion of less empowered people like the elderly or people with disabilities, the awareness of the women-animal interactions (both as carers and as feeling safer), to specific animal assisted activities, to plan the presence of animals in hospitals, sheltered residences and kindergartens or broader innovative services linked to tourism or everyday life.

I

I CAN MINDSET

The I CAN Mindset is a mentality grounded in the belief that all people can be protagonists of their own lives, trusting in their abilities to solve challenges. In order to reach the I CAN Mindset, IN-HABIT follows a methodology that uses the principles of design thinking to make a formula for the I CAN. This “formula” intentionally cultivates the I CAN Mindset through five steps: Feel, Do, Imagine, Evolve and Share.

This methodology gives the people the empowerment of conviction to do something to change their environment, set their own challenges, change their lives through their own ideas and their own knowledge. Every story and idea is valued and listened to which gives them the conviction, the empowerment to change the world.

INCLUSIVE TRANSFORMATION PLAN (ITPLAN)

The IN-HABIT Inclusive Transformation Plans are the Action Plans resulting from the **co-design** processes implemented with a GDEI perspective in the four **IN-HUBs**. These processes will be conducted with relevant stakeholders and local inhabitants and led by IN-HABIT city partners and trained facilitators to determine the spatial and functional elements of the IN-HUBs, as well as the foreseen **VIS** to boost **IHW** in the selected urban areas.

INCLUSIVE TRANSITION PATHWAYS (ITPATH)

Inclusive Transition Pathway (ITPath) stands for the multi-stakeholder participatory strategy developed within IN-HABIT, aimed at leading the co-design and implementation of local projects. It aims at the sustainable and equitable use of re-designed public spaces in each city, with particular attention to the needs of people at risk of discrimination and exclusion. ITPaths consists of context-specific and inclusive co-management schemes defined with the involvement of local stakeholders. They include a set of innovative financial schemes (e.g., community bartering, agreements of collaboration, social-public procurement schemes) to boost inclusive management and sustainable economic exploitation of regenerated spaces, to ensure full ownership and an equal and fair distribution of benefits (social economic, health-related) derived from the VIS. The ITP also includes the organisational model and specific functions of potential IN-HUBs in each city, which should function as a common pool resource agency to meet the demand and offer of voluntary work related to the sustainable co-management of re-designed public spaces. ITPs can be neither predesigned nor applied context-blinded. Each city will have its own ITP resulting from common principles of IN-HABIT and the co-design process with local stakeholders. This customisation is crucial to guarantee that context-dependent issues and potentialities are taken into account.

The creation of ITPaths will benefit from a common methodology for designing and managing public participation. The methodology will be shared during the training of **Local Activators**.

INCLUSIVE HEALTH & WELLBEING (IHW)

Inclusive Health and Well-Being relate to an equitable distribution of health and well-being in a society, in a way that takes particular account of the needs of groups vulnerable to discrimination and exclusion such as the elderly, women, migrants, ethnic minorities, LGBTIQ+ people and persons with disabilities.

IN-HABIT addresses mental health, socioeconomic well-being, and healthy lifestyles as essential dimensions of health and well-being. IN-HABIT views inclusive health and well-being as **co-created common pool resources** - resources that benefit the entire community (our 'commons') and require the investment of the entire community to be governed and preserved. In order to co-design, co-deploy and co-manage health and well-being in an inclusive, innovative and sustainable manner, IN-HABIT uses a **polycentric governance** approach and a **Gender, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion perspective** based on behavioural change.

INCLUSIVE HEALTH & WELLBEING ASSESSMENT (IHW-A)

Inclusive Health & Wellbeing (IHW) Assessment assesses the impact of co-deployed solutions in terms of changes affecting mental health, socio-economic well-being and healthy life-

styles of people in the re-designed city areas. New and complementary impact indicators on IHW at an urban level will be co-designed. A sustainable and interoperable data platform will be established, securing open, consistent data about the impacts of the deployed solutions. A participative and inclusive monitoring system will be tested to measure benefits and capture the multiple co-benefits of innovations (including social, cultural, technical, digital and nature-based innovations).

INCLUSIVE HEALTH & WELLBEING INDICATORS (IHW-I)

IHW Indicators are a set of context-based key impact indicators to measure the changes produced by the IN-HABIT project on citizens' inclusive health and wellbeing in the four pilot cities. They are co-developed with the involvement of local citizens and city partners, starting from the analysis and adaptation of existing indicators on subjective well-being at European and International level (OECD, Eurostat, European Commission, UNDP/SDGs, other H2020-funded projects) in order to ensure comparability and to fill the gaps in terms of data availability on sustainable urban development for small and medium sized cities. IHW indicators consider both the researcher's and the citizens' assumptions on expected changes affecting health and well-being, with specific regard to the perspective of those people who identified themselves as representatives of the groups with Gender and Diversity personal characteristics at a local level.

IN-HABIT APP

IN-HABIT App is a tool for information provision and policy change. It provides city maps with information and nudges about the use and enjoyment of the city based on geo-localised pins consisting of multiple layers. These layers provide different perspectives which allow both users and policy makers not just to use the city and help improve it from their own perspective (e.g., safe, healthy, accessible or cheap routes through the city, events, fun and activities for children, tourist routes with audio-storytelling, etc.), but also to understand how the city is experienced by other groups, encouraging both perspective taking and tailoring of interventions. IN-HABIT App is designed on the basis of the latest principles of behavioural science, constantly updated by real data from real registered users at different levels, made available to the cities for planning and decision-making. It provides both horizontal nudging (peer-to-peer) at various levels to enable collaboration, co-creation and co-enjoyment of the city, but also vertical nudging: top-down (from policy makers to citizens) and bottom-up (from citizens to policy makers).

IN-HABIT PLATFORM

The IN-HABIT data Platform is designed and implemented to ensure continuous communication and collaboration among the **IN-HUB stakeholders** within and across the cities. The Platform will store open and consistent data on the performance and impacts of the deployed solutions in a secure, long-term and sustainable manner. It will be used for co-design and monitoring purposes, to collect data, for impact assessment purposes and for communication and dissemination activities. The IN-HABIT platform is created to integrate, manage and visualise data at city level from various sources. Data about air pollution and temperature, movements of people and vehicles, noise, landscape features and wellness spots are assembled to pro-

duce interactive scenarios, GIS-mapping and spatial/environmental analysis in real time. The platform integrates data from the different participative layers and monitoring sources, which include sensors, traffic cameras, open data, mobile app, IoT, street sensors, big data, observational programmes such as Copernicus and GEOSS, and citizens' observatories. IN-HABIT platform is built over FIWARE components for data acquisition and interconnectivity of layers that guarantees an open, robust and compliant with data protection regulation, ensuring cybersecurity and contributing with the interoperability among different communication standards. The huge amount of data and the use of continuous 'big data' analytics (high dimensional multi-view data) creates an intelligent system for **IHW** in city management. Prediction and optimisation techniques based on deep neural networks will allow the connectivity between different subsystems and the smart management of infrastructures. The IN-HABIT platform (accessible by web) is connected to other city or regional data management systems with the intention to bring together decision makers, operators and citizens. The platform will use and integrate data from the **IN-HABIT App**, which uses geolocation for collaborative urban planning, citizen engagement and monitoring.

IN-HUBS

The IN-HUB is a laboratory of social innovation where people coming from different public and private organisations or as individual citizens work together for social change. It is a networking strategy for the enhancement of cooperation aimed at the co-design and co-management of spaces and a platform for structural dialogue and collaboration. **IN-HUBs** are both physical places for meeting and sharing, and organisational structures to facilitate the transformative process.

INTERCULTURAL AND CREATIVE FOOD HUB

An intercultural and creative food hub is a multifunctional space that is intended not only as a food hub for sustainably-produced and locally-sourced food, but also as a recreational and educational space. The hub aims to promote healthy and sustainable food habits, as well as social and cultural integration and cohesion, which is done by: (1) promoting healthy lifestyles and food consumption habits among local people, particularly the most vulnerable (e.g. elderly, children), and discouraging sedentary lifestyles and unhealthy diets; (2) improving accessibility for all while encouraging sustainable mobility (e.g. walking and cycling) from and to the hub; (3) using food as a means to improve intercultural and intergenerational social relations, create a sense of belonging and ownership of the place; and (4) shortening food supply chains and decreasing food waste in the market.

INTERSECTIONALITY

Intersectionality refers to the fact that people have multiple identities as a result of various factors, including their upbringing, social relations and history, but also because of the work of institutions and power structures. Recognition of intersectionality helps to reveal the potential forms of discrimination and disadvantage that result from the combination of the individuals' layered identities.

K

KEY IMPACT INDICATORS (KII)

Key Impact Indicators (KIIs) measure the changes produced by the project compared to a baseline. They can be quantitative (expressed in numbers or rates) or qualitative (expressed in phenomena, general trends, examples, typifications).

L

LOCAL/COMMUNITY ACTIVATORS

Local/community activators are researchers and community facilitators in the local context. Two community activators speaking both English and the local language will be hired in each city. They support local stakeholder/citizen engagement, identifying community leaders, networks and organisations working for social change. They reach out to people living in the neighbourhood, with specific attention to those at risk of exclusion and discrimination, in order to engage them in co-designing and **co-creating** project solutions. Secondly, they support university teams and other project partner organisations in desk and field research: taking care of secondary data collection through networking with local private and public entities; translating and making reports on data collection; taking care of primary data collection through interviews, questionnaires, workshops and focus groups and writing down the related reports. The Local/community activators are empowered through the training provided by TSR and other WP5 partners to perform digital communication tasks, gender-based and diversity-based research and impact assessment activities, organisation and animation of events and citizen engagement, co-design and research tasks in the field.

LOCAL OBSERVERS/COMMUNITY REPRESENTATIVES

Local observers are representatives of local organisations, enterprises, groups and citizens who are interested in the project and will be actively involved in the co-design, co-management and evaluation/assessment of the IN-HABIT solutions. There will be about 15 per city, they will speak the local language and are the core group of the local **IN-HUBs**. Among them, there should be representatives of citizens usually less/not involved in public decision making and participative processes including groups at risk of exclusion and discrimination (elderly, ethnic minorities, low-income people, children, LGBTIQ+ people, persons with disabilities).

They can also be representatives of associations, active in the neighbourhood and have experience with the life in the neighbourhood and are able to give feedback on the neighbourhood's life and changes that have occurred over time.

They are encouraged to act as key actors and multipliers among their own social groups. They are reached and involved in all project activities also through the provision of non-monetary incentives by means of networking action run by the **community activators**. They will be involved throughout the time in the assessment of the project's impact with a **GDEI** perspective by granting an inclusive approach to health and well-being.

M

MINDSET CHANGE

A mindset is a mental attitude. It shapes our actions and our thoughts. Our mindset is our way of thinking, and our way of thinking can limit or empower oneself, in any number of ways.

Mindsets are considered to be a range of self-beliefs, with a fixed mindset on one end of a scale and a growth mindset on the other. Within this range, people with a fixed mindset believe their basic qualities, like their intelligence or talent, are simply fixed traits. A growth mindset implies a belief that people can change their ability through effort. The main contrast between the two types of mindsets is around the idea of change. When people believe their abilities can change, they have greater perceived self-control over their outcomes, and it creates a love for learning and a resilience that is essential for great accomplishment.

N

NATURE BASED SOLUTIONS (NBS)

NBS are actions inspired by, supported by or copied from nature; both using and enhancing existing solutions to challenges, as well as exploring more novel solutions that replicate the features and complex system processes of nature. NBS are cost-effective, simultaneously pro-

vide environmental, social and economic benefits and help build resilience. Such solutions work with and enhance natural habitats to help address societal challenges, including helping people adapt to the effects of change and disasters. NBS are supposed to contribute positively to social inclusiveness even beyond their functions to increase social well being, health and quality of life for urban residents, whilst also protecting the ecosystems on which we depend. Key examples include the restoration of coastal ecosystems to protect communities from storm surges and erosion, agroforestry to stabilise crop yields in drier climates, and forest restoration to regulate water supplies and protect against flooding and landslides.

P

PARTICIPATIVE STORYTELLING

Storytelling is an essential act of community building. Participative (participatory) storytelling is an inclusive methodology aimed at empowering people with the capacity to express their voice, define their identity and share their values through collective narration processes. Participatory storytelling methodologies have the scope to fill the gap with subjects that may have no voice nor channels to express themselves, and facilitate the accessible formulation of key concepts to reach out to those more at risk of exclusion. Participative storytelling does not have a focus on specific languages and media, it is open to the use of audio, video, photography, drawing and any possible combination of forms of expression to collect personal memories, impressions and ideas and reconstitute them in accessible formats.

Participative storytelling will be employed in IN-HABIT to support the co-design process, to engage youth and other target groups and to keep citizens informed and engaged with the local activities of the **IN-HUBs**, as well as to support impact assessment.

POLYCENTRIC GOVERNANCE

Polycentric governance refers to a governance system in which multiple governing bodies interact to make and enforce rules within a specific policy arena or location. It is considered to be an effective way to achieve collective action in the face of changes requiring adaptation and resilience.

PROJECT PARTNERS

Project Partners of IN-HABIT are all the organisations that are directly funded by the H2020 grant to develop the aims of the project. They represent a balanced mix of administration, academia, third sector and enterprise responding to the quadruple helix model for social innovation. IN-HABIT is a unique consortium gathering in each city a research institution, a city au-

thority and a grass-roots organisation, and wrapped up by experts in citizen engagement and social urban planning, gender and diversity, impact measurement, business coaching, behaviour change, advanced technologies, creative activities and communication, all of them aiming to build capacities at city level.

PUBLIC-PRIVATE-PEOPLE PARTNERSHIPS

Public-Private-People Partnership is an emerging concept addressing the inclusion of a larger spectrum of actors, specifically NGOs, civil-society and informal subjectivities, in planning processes. The 4-*P*s model has arisen to respond to the limits of the traditional public-private partnership, and accompanies the criticism of the mere dichotomy between market and public sector, acknowledging the role of the common good as an essential third pillar in steering societal processes. Public-Private-People partnerships aim to create more inclusive governance involving different actors, addressing the problems of exclusion and lack of transparency, including citizens' knowledge, more effectively and creating environments and services that respond better to the needs of inhabitants. IN-HABIT's strong focus on the GDEI engagement process responds to the explicit goal to enforce the "fourth *P*" in the territorial governance steered by the **IN-HUBs**.

R

RIGHT TO THE CITY

As geographer David Harvey put it, the right to the city is far more than the individual liberty to access urban resources: it is a right to change ourselves by changing the city. Since the publication in 1968 of Henri Lefevbre's *Le droit a la ville*, this formulation has become the "cry and demand" for rights in cities around the world. From the claims of the student movement and situationist agitators, throughout the multifaceted experience of the urban movements of the last fifty years, the right to the city as a concept has settled globally in the academic discourses and in the everyday practice of citizens and policy makers. In 2016 it was adopted in the New Urban Agenda at the Habitat III United Nations Conference on Housing and Sustainable Urban Development in Quito, Ecuador, and endorsed by the United Nations General Assembly at its sixty-eighth plenary meeting of the seventy-first session on the 23rd of December 2016. According to this document, "The right to the city should be considered as a new paradigm for urban development that seeks to address the major challenges in cities and human settlements of rapid urbanization, poverty reduction, social exclusion, and environmental risk that call for decisive actions and new policy priorities by national, regional, and local governments". The three pillars of the RTC as identified by the Urban Agenda are: spatially just resource distribution, political agency, and social, economic and cultural diversity.

REVERSIBLE MULTIFUNCTIONAL OPEN-SOURCE URBAN LANDSCAPE – REMOULD

Reversible Multifunctional Open-source Urban Landscape – REMOULD - is an urban planning approach aimed at integrating public, residential and commercial spaces in a transformable and adaptable way to the changing needs of the area. It does not only focus on a physical environment with built elements, but also on an atmosphere inspired and defined by people, cultures, art and nature. Its open-source nature increases the sense of co-ownership of public spaces by assigning specific uses by the users themselves.

IN-HABIT uses this approach in Nitra with the participation of landscape architects, artists, migrants, students, social entrepreneurs, relevant organisations and local residents. The co-deployment process relies strongly on the DIY culture of the community, while economic sustainability is promoted through innovative business models (public craft workshops/DIY café, food booths, bike-sharing services and repair shops). It consists of multifunctional urban mobiliary elements integrating interactive lighting solutions and experimental gardens, whose reversibility provides a platform for social, cultural, educational and sport activities (e.g., art exhibitions, art therapy, theatre). The flexibility of the approach also increases the replicability of this solution.

S

SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED CITIES (SMSCs)

While the mainstream discourse about the urban age focuses on the fact that the majority of the planetary population lives in cities, what is often less acknowledged is that a significant percentage of this urban population live in small and medium-sized cities (SMSCs). The European pattern of settlement depends considerably on smaller-size urban areas with populations between 5,000 and 100,000 inhabitants which play an important role in determining Europe's polycentric urban structure. Yet this dimension is largely undervalued in academic research and policy making. IN-HABIT brings a specific focus on SMSCs and IHW. The smaller size may facilitate the organisation of services and make it easier and more feasible to meet citizens' needs, but on the other hand, it may pose challenges in terms of economies of scale, the on-site availability of certain advanced technical competences, including language barriers, or the fiscal basis to sustain investments in public infrastructure. Europe faces important R&I gaps to cater for the needs of these smaller cities since urban research and solutions are context-specific and the specific R&I needs of peripheral SMSCs have by far received significantly less attention.

STAKEHOLDER

Stakeholder is a catch-all term. It identifies any subjectivity that has or may have an interest in a project or programme. In disciplinary language from business to policy it can assume dif-

ferent connotations. Within IN-HABIT, we keep the meaning of the term very open to capture the essential focus of the project on inclusiveness, and the processes of stakeholder mapping and engagement will be essentially dedicated to reaching out to less represented social components that are more at risk of exclusion.

In business models, the stakeholders are often categorised through the acronym UGIP, representing the four main categories: Users, Governance, Influencers, Providers. This model does not differ substantially from the quadruple helix social innovation model proposed in social sciences adopting civil society, government, academia and industry as the essential agencies shaping social change. It is important to understand that the stakeholder is not defined by any formal legal status or organisation: single individuals and informal coalitions are equally understood as legitimate stakeholders as long as they have established an interest or a relation with a given context.

SYSTEMIC IMPACT FRAMEWORK

Systemic Impact Framework is a multidimensional approach for the assessment of the impacts of the **visionary and integrated solutions** that aims at detecting the interconnections among social, relational, health and economic outcomes on one hand, as well as the interrelations among well-being and cultural, digital, nature based and social innovations.

U

URBAN RECONNAISSANCE

Urban Reconnaissance is a cognitive approach defined by the ogino:knauss collective and developed by Tesserae as a methodological device for the holistic investigation of the urbanisation process. It is based on a set of 64 different definitions of the word “city”, all referring to different epistemological perspectives and disciplinary approaches. Arranged in a circle, the 64 keywords encompass the urban field, illustrating at once the impossibility of understanding the urban dimension only from a single perspective and the necessity to adopt specific angles to provide depth of vision. The various definitions are connected by hyperlinks, illustrating their complex interrelation. Each definition is associated with an exercise, suggesting modes and methods of surveying a territory from a specific perspective. Urban Reconnaissance is employed by Tesserae as the initial praxis to disentangle the complexity of factors that constitute every urban identity and is proposed to IN-HABIT as an exercise for facilitating the exhaustive assessment of the contextual conditions of projects and the inclusive co-design of solutions.

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